

Studies in Litigation Against the Church in Nigeria: The Case of Basilica of Grace, Abbi

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Abstract:

This study captures in vivid perspectives, the legal battles that the Church has come to face in recent times in Nigeria over land. For this case-study that is focused on the Basilica of Grace, Abbi in Ndokwa West Local Government Area of Delta State Nigeria, attempt shall be made to concentrate on the legal struggles the Church began to face in recent times arising from land hunger and the emergence of the commercializing influence of capitalism on the Church in Nigeria. The Church in Nigeria has become hugely wealthy that attack on it has become quite fashionable with the hope and aim that in the calculated process of litigating with the Church

over land, the Church may cave into settlement with the disputants and in the process, the disputants may 'hack into the finances of the Church' and 'chop out a large chunk-of-cash from the tilt of the Church' in order for the Church to have peace. This study which adopts the doctrinal method interrogates the circumstances that led the Basilica of Grace, Abbi (under the Registered Trustees of Diocese of Ndokwa Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion) into a pernicious legal battle with Femi Ojuyenum and six others representing Ogwezzi-Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street of Abbi. The study traces the origin of the grant of the land to the Church, the ceding of a part to the State for School as a Missionary Society and the pseudo reversionary claim of the Ogwezzi-Amacha family and the conveyance of same to unscrupulous 'money bags' in Abbi community who have taken turns to transfer the land in millions from one 'Barron' to another to the discomfiture of the Church at Abbi. It further interrogates the legal processes and pleadings of the parties through the trial court to the various appellate courts in details and captures the socio-legal influences driving the litigation. The study finds that those who dabbled into the litigation with the Basilica of Grace did so for selfish interest and in a calculated desire to upturn the grant made by the early fathers of Abbi community to the Christian Missionary Society on the spurious claims that those forefathers who made the grant in relative antiquity were merely overwhelmed by European civilizing influence and uninformed of the ancient and current value of land. The study found further that the litigation was being fought in the face of a customary arbitration against the antagonists of the Church. The study therefore suggests and recommends that the claims and attacks against the grant and the Church should be repudiated and dropped by the defendants to 'allow sleeping dog lie'.

Keywords: *Bias, Corruption, Church, Land Dispute, Customary Arbitration, Umu-Onyugba.*

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Introduction

The litigations against the Church in Nigeria over land are viral. The Landlords and resident of the Royal Garden Community Development Association had accused the Believers Love World (Christ Embassy) of encroaching on their land in Aseese in Obafemi Owode Local Government Area of Ogun State (Lambo, 2022). Iwaya community in Lagos had upturned the judgments of the High Court and Court of Appeal over a large parcel of land in a dispute of over 33 years against the Anglican Church. The Supreme Court in the Iwaya community case had followed an earlier 1972 decision in *Registered Trustees of Apostolic Church v. A.G. Midwestern Nigeria* where it was held that a Church has the onus to prove that it was incorporated through a certificate of incorporation before it can be deemed in law to own landed property as such, the evidence that the Anglican Church was an unregistered entity at the time the dispute commenced before the trial High Court is fatal to the victories it had secured in the two lower courts (Sahara Reporters, 2017). In Ilara Village in Sagamu Local Government Area of Ogun State, the plaintiffs in HOS/130/2015 claimed against the Redeemed Christian Church of God that they had acquired the land in dispute many years before the Church surfaced in the area and claimed damages in the sum of N100million (Kayode-Adedeji, 2015).

In *Registered Trustees of the Victorious Army Ministry International, Justice Gbadebo Oshola* held that the Ashade Royal family of Ogba (represented by Alhaji M. Ashade and Prince O. Ashade) in Lagos State was the rightful persons entitled to the statutory right of occupancy over the land on Acme Crescent in Ikeja area through compelling, credible and conclusive evidence of ownership and the Church has proceeded on appeal to the Court of Appeal, Lagos (Soyele, 2023). Justice Olugboyega Ogunfowora of Ogun State High Court has also dismissed an application by Registered Trustees of World Mission Agency Incorporated (Winners Chapel) against the Ogunseye family over 13 acres of

land where the Church has built its Covenant University along Idiroko Road in Ogun State. The family claimed that by virtue of the judgment in Appeal No CA/1/126/2010 delivered on 13th July, 2017 it is the owner of the 13 acres and alternatively claimed the sum of N4billion being the current value of the land (Ojo, 2020). In the case involving Methodist Boys High School and the Church, while the Church is desirous of selling part of its land for development of luxurious flats with third parties in a project tagged 'The Wesley' the Alumni of the School is vehemently opposed to the dream of the Church because it is 'thinking outside the box' of scholarship and the spiritual mission of the School (Ogundare, 2022).

In Obosi in Idemili North Local Government Area of Anambra State, the on-going land dispute between the community and Olu Ndi Enigwe Adoration Ministry has led to destruction of buildings and properties of the Church to the tune of millions of naira and persistent attempts at bringing the imbroglio to bail by the State and other agencies have not yielded much results (Ogunyemi, 2022). One cardinal issue which has been identified with the Church in relation to its acquisition of land and landed property in Nigeria and even all over the world is the hazy manner it follows in the due process of acquisition of land and landed property. Because the Church is associated with godly things, Akinloye (2020) has submitted that the increasing number of legal disputes involving the Church is largely in the nature and management of land belonging to Churches in Nigeria. There is a perceivable failure of the Church in its observation of due diligence and compliance with civil law standards regarding acquisition of property.

It shall be clearly found in this study, for instance, that there is no concrete documentation of how the Basilica of Grace, Abbi acquired the land at Umu-Onyugba Street Abbi. If as shall be demonstrated from the case of the Church that it was granted the land by Abbi community or Abbi Traditional Council as alleged by their opponents, the Ogwezzi-

Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street, Abbi there ought to have been a document of the grant in vivid detailing. Although there is incidental document such as a survey plan (which was also not duly registered) and written communications within the Church, those documents strictly speaking cannot be passed-off as legal document of title. The attempt of the representative of the Church while in the witness box to give a traditional history of the Church (before his tactical withdrawal alleging sundry issues) did not also fall firmly on concrete templates as enunciated by the Supreme Court in *Idundun v Okumagba* (SC. 309/74) where the five methodologies of proving title to land in Nigeria were laid down. The Church could hanker to rely on long and undisturbed possession but it is equally the law that however long a possession of a piece of land could be it cannot ripen into ownership especially as the original owner is signaling to the concepts of intimidation, hoodwinking, manipulation, blackmail and connivance, forcible entry without consent and reversion or revisionism.

It shall however be noted in the course of this study that what is admitted need not be proved. It is the statutory law that no fact needs be proved in any civil proceedings which the parties to the proceedings or their agents agree to admit at the hearing, or which, before the hearing, they agree to admit by any writing under their hands or which by any rule or pleading in force at the time they are deemed to have admitted by their pleadings. Furthermore, proof shall not be required of a fact the knowledge of which is not reasonably open to question and which is: common knowledge in the locality in which the proceeding is being held (Section 123, Evidence Act 2021; *Ndayako & Ors v. Dantoro & Ors* (2004) 18 NSCQR 646 and *Lagos State Government & Ors v. Adulkareem & Ors* (2022) 17 NWLR (Pt.1859 213 at 335). That the Basilica of Grace was granted the land in dispute is notorious and general knowledge in Abbi but mere admission of that fact does not absolve the Church from proving so in a declaratory relief as sought by the Church in the action under conversation. This is because it is a cardinal principle of Nigerian land law that he who

alleges must prove and a claimant in a declaratory action is to succeed on the strength of his case and not on the weakness of the defence. However, the claimant is also at liberty to rely on the evidence of the defendants which supports its case. Although the customary arbitration award and the registration or incorporation of the Church may be in good standing, it would not be out of scope for the Church to have a certificate of occupancy from the Ndokwa West Local Government Council or the Governor of Delta State.

Statement of the problem

The desire to take back land from Church Missionary Society for sundry reasons is currently an open-wound festering in both government and communal spaces. At communal level, the fight to take back what was given to the missions began to rear its ugly head in the 1980s when government began to increase the number of schools and in Delta State and perhaps Niger delta region, it began with the administration of Professor Ambrose Ali which desired and pursued the policy that all communities should participate with the government to establish community secondary schools in addition to the introduction of free education at all levels. There was a significant invasion of the mission schools and their take over by government. The fall out of the takeovers was the emergence of some 'loose plots of land' either abandoned by the missions or not properly cultivated by the acquiring State. Such vacant plots began to experience and drive squabbles from all manners of claims by individuals, families and communities leading to land disputes.

The Abbi Traditional Council identified the problem when it decided in its customary arbitral award that 'The Palace will not dispossess the Anglican Church of the land given to it for a very long period. This will create a dangerous precedence which might lead other original owners to claim their land to other missions and bodies'. What occurred at Umu-Onyugba Abbi in Ndokwa West Local Government Area of Delta State has been replicated in the

neighbouring Ezionum community in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State where the C.M.S. Church faced a similarly prolonged litigation against it from the Emekene family, the original owners of the land donated to the Church at Ogbe-Ofu quarters, Ezionum. At Ashaka community in Ndokwa East Local Government Area, Delta State the Miligu family also disputed and tried to oust the Church and the Ozoma Uku Primary School from the land the ancestors of the family granted to the Church so many years ago. The same scenario has been found in Emu Unor in Ndokwa West Local Government Area where the Nduka family has held down the Catholic Church in a land dispute premised on reversionary rights on going for several years. What is driving these legal skirmishes are complicated and are interrogated in this paper.

Conceptual clarification

The Basilica of Grace, Abbi

The Anglican Church at Abbi was introduced by Mr. Ishicheli Onyenuwe from Ukanabo-Uku Street in about 1911. He firstly heard about the group at Obiarukwu and journeyed there to join the group and registered his membership with three pence. On his returned he converted friends including Paul Oyemike, Emekene Ishie, James Omogor, John Onwudegu, and Peter Urada. Later they journeyed to Sapele in a delegation and met Rev. Ologundudu and later sent a mission to Onitsha where they were referred back to the Superintendent in Charge of Asaba District where they were received and told that by 1912 they would receive Senior Catechist Asieku. By 1925 a Church building and a School had been established and the land in dispute became the second location after Umia Primary School, Abbi called location one. It was the first School in the entire region servicing Emu, Ezionum, Ogume, Orogun, Owhe Ologbo etc (Oweh, 2018, p. 169).

A second account of the emergence of the first Church at Abbi can be found in Abbi: Her History, People and Culture (Eka-Iloma, 2017 p. 193 – 194). Although with a slight variation in

dates, the first Christian mission to come to Abbi in 1916 is Church Missionary Society. 'That year four men embraced Christianity abandoning their idols. They were: Onwudegu who was christened John; Oshike Oyemike who was christened Paul; Ekelegu who was christened Joseph and one Orada who was christened Peter. These young Christians trekked to Sapele to ask that a small Church be approved for them at Abbi. They were referred to C.M.S. Headquarters at Asaba. In their doggedness they marched to Asaba. It was at Asaba they approved for them a Church and as a result one Catechist was posted to Abbi. As soon as this happened many others joined the Church.' The St. John's C.M.S. School, Abbi (Basilica of Grace), was founded in 1925 (Eka-Iloma, p. 195).

Ogwezzi-Amacha family

This is one of the aboriginal families of Abbi. The Amacha group is said to be the first group to migrate from Achala in eastern Nigeria to Aboh across the River Niger according to Oweh's account. But Eka-Iloma's account places them last of the three patriarchs of Ewolokpo, Ogwezhi and Udu. The Patriarch of the group, Ogwezzi Amacha, left Aboh for Ushie and eventually found his way with his elder brother (Ukwata who founded Umukwata) to Abbi. His son, Udu, later led the group to prominence in Abbi. Their claim in this study to be the autonomous people and original founders of the land in dispute is indisputable and indestructible. What may excite some debates however, are the circumstances in which they granted the land to the Church in relative antiquity. If they granted the land through their ancestors, they should also be able to discharge the burden of how the grant was made. The instrument through which their ancestors made the grant should be handy.

To the extent that there is no handy instrument through which the land passed from the family to the Church, the claim of the Ogwezzi-Amacha in intimidation, manipulation, hoodwinking and forcible entry without consent and consequently reversion, become quite plausible. But the stubborn issue which both

parties in the dispute cannot disavow is that the relationship appears to be so aged that none of the present contestants can figure out what actually happened and the circumstances in which the grant was made. One theory which may lie behind the foliage of facts and which can be deduced from the accounts of Eka-Iloma (2017, p. 209) is the conquest of Abbi in 1914. The first visitation of the Whiteman to Abbi was recorded in 1905 and thereafter the 'Abbi war of 1914 with the Colonial Masters brought in its trail Christianity and education'. One of the recognized ways of proving title to land under traditional evidence is conquest. But throughout the gamut of the claims of the Church, the Basilica of Grace has not alluded to the fact that her acquisition of the land in dispute was through the Abbi conquest of 1914. Even a close and critical survey of the circumstances that led to the war equally has nothing to depict that it was associated with land dispute. Rather it had to do with political struggle. But there is no doubt that given the superior military power of the Europeans (the British in particular) and its indistinguishable relationship with Christianity, the need for land and the grant of same by Traditional institutions to the Churches is largely 'for and or by the asking'.

Theoretical framework

Historical revisionism

Revisionism has recently acquired significant glamour and its application to the discussion of modern phenomenon is quite persuasive. It is the critical re-examination of presumed historical facts or a reinterpretation of recorded history but whether it is practically beneficial is a debate that runs deep (Revisionism – Wikipedia & Historical Revisionism). Thusly, revisionism is all about asking questions about and trying to change existing beliefs about how events happened. It is a term used with both positive and negative connotations for any scholarly practice dedicated to revising an established position (Revisionism: English meaning – Cambridge & Revisionism – Oxford Reference). If in this study the Ogwezzi-Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street and their learned Solicitor,

C. J. Enegide Esq., are described as revisionists, it means that they reject the traditionally held beliefs about a particular historical event or phenomenon (Revisionist definition and meaning – Collins English Dictionary). And that event and phenomenon in the circumstances of this study is the role played by the early missionaries and their relationship with the Traditional administration or Council in Abbi community particularly with regard to how land was acquired for the purposes of the 'civilizing mission' and for what purposes the lands acquired were used: did the people of Abbi benefit from the mission or was it as characterized by Ogwezzi-Amacha family and C. J. Enegide Esq.? How do the family and its legal luminary reconcile their views and positions with the arbitral award of the Ukor-Okpala-in-Council of His Royal Highness Uzu Nwachukwu, the Ukor-Okpala of Abbi on 7th November, 2011?

For the Basilica of Grace, the coming of the Church to Abbi is perhaps the greatest phenomenon of our age as it came with modern housing, medicals, education, worship, water, light and road. But to Ogwezzi-Amacha and the family's Counsel, they took their choicest and strategically located and well sought after lands through blackmail, intimation and hoodwinking that the lands are needed for the development of the general good whereas, the missionaries were to allow only the converted to access these civilizing influences. Therefore, the opportunity of taking back their lands is now. The table must turn and their reversionary right must be ignited as the lands were previously taken without their consent or informed consent.

Theory of judicial corruption

The Nigerian judiciary is one arm of government that has been greatly afflicted by the corrupting influence of the society. A corrupt society cannot beget a 'clean' judiciary as it is notorious that 'you cannot give what you do not have'. It is a significant point to make that at the conclusion of this study in 2023 which concerns a dispute that arose before 7th November, 2011 when the customary arbitration went in favour of the Basilica of Grace, indeed after more than

a decade, the ownership of the Umu-Onyugba land has not been decided by the Nigerian courts. The preliminary applications of injunction to preserve the res has just ended before the Court of Appeal on 5th June, 2023 and that is if the Ogwezzi-Amacha family would not appeal the decision of the Court of Appeal to the Supreme Court of Nigeria in order to further obfuscate the dispute. Indeed, when the case was listed before the Ndokwa West Area Customary Court, Kwale after the decision of the High Court of Justice Kwale that the case should be heard there de novo, the vehemence with which the Ogwezzi-Amacha family resisted the hearing on the ground that it had appealed against the judgment of the said High Court of Justice to the Court of Appeal, Asaba was so strong that the influence of *lis pendens* in the case was touchy. Third parties who had acquired interest in the land while the litigation is pending were rather ‘fistful’. When litigation has been bought by buying a land in dispute, more litigation is ignited.

The role of Nigerian judges in the influence and permeation of corruption within the fabric of the courts has so much to do. Just one incident of the trial court refusing to decline from adjudication due to accusation of corruption and bias attendant to it, has led to so much delay in the final determination of the case of the Basilica of Grace against the Ogwezzi-Amacha family. In this case, although the appellate High Court of Justice, Kwale declined to pronounce that the Presiding Chairman of the District Customary Court, Abbi was corrupt because the forum was not the proper court to say so, the Court found that *‘it is obvious that he may not only have issues with applicant but he also had issues with Counsel to applicant which he exhibited in court and he caused same to becloud his sense of reasoning which is most unbecoming of a judge’*. This study is not primed on the conduct of the Presiding Chairman of the District Court, Abbi but it has certainly touch-lighted the place of Presiding Officers in the quest for justice in Nigeria to the extent that it could be perfunctorily submitted that justice is for the ‘highest bidder in a bazaar that the Courts have turned into in Nigeria’ and in which there are proxy-litigations for as the Ogwezzi-Amacha

family appears in court, they are not actually the ones in the contentions and litigations but those who have ‘tycoon money’ who bought up its so-called reversionary interest in the land in dispute.

Theory of customary arbitration

The philosophy behind customary arbitration has more to do with revisionism than constitutionalism. The Supreme Court bent backwards to reconstruct it and integrate it into the legal mainstream given that in English law arbitration has been fully developed with sufficient judicial authority and recognition. Reading through the cases in Nigeria, it appears the most recognized authority in the enunciation of the general principles of customary arbitration is the case of *Agu v. Ikewibe* (1991) 3 LRCN 686. For instance, in *Iheanacho v Chigere* (2004) 121 LRCN 4940 at 4961 the Supreme Court gave the foregoing indication when it held that ‘the essential nature and legal implication of a customary arbitration are as explained in the case of *Agu v Ikewibe*. In the case, the Supreme Court enunciated the philosophical framework thusly, ‘a customary arbitration is not an exercise of the judicial power of the constitution not being a function undertaken by the courts *and customary law is by virtue of section 274 (3) (4) (b) an existing law being a body of rule of law in force immediately before the coming into force of the Constitution 1979 (now the 1999 Constitution)*’.

The Supreme Court then proceeded to construct the principles as follows, ‘where a body of persons act as arbitrators over a dispute between two parties, their decision shall have a binding effect if it is shown that both parties submitted to the arbitrators, accepted the terms of the arbitration and agreed to be bound by the decision.’ The apex court in the same locus classicus settled that ‘where parties voluntarily submit their dispute to a non-judicial body for determination and indicate their willingness to be bound by the decision of the non-judicial body or freedom to reject the decision where not satisfied and that neither of the parties has declined from the decision so pronounced, *Nigerian law recognizes such arbitration at customary law which is different from that under statute*’. Having laid down the general principles in *Agu v.*

Ikewibe, the Supreme Court went on in *Umeadi & Ors v. Chibunze & Anor.* (2020) 303 LRCN 40 at 65 to demonstrate that ‘there are a plethora of superior authorities to the effect that if customary arbitration was pleaded and proved as such, it was binding on the parties and capable of constituting estoppel’. Such plethora of authorities signified in *Umeadi* in 2020 can be found in the 2001 and 2002 cases of *Odonigi v Oyeleke* (2001) 84 LRCN 658 at 675 and *Egesimba v. Onuzurike* (2002) 103 LRCN 2485 at 2506.

In *Egesimba*, the classical case of *Agu v. Ikewibe* wherein the general principles were laid down was straightened out into items as follows, ‘where a body of men, be they chiefs or otherwise, act as arbitrators over a dispute between two parties, their decision shall have a binding effect, if it is shown *firstly* that both submitted to the arbitration. *Secondly* that they accepted the terms of the arbitration. *Thirdly* that they agreed to be bound by the decision, such decision has the same *authority as the judgment of a judicial body and will be binding on the parties and create estoppel*’. Additional but incidental principles were added in the case of *Okoye & Anor v Obiaso & Ors* (2010) 186 LRCN 181 at 466 bringing them up to five thusly: a party can prove the existence of a customary arbitration by pleading and establishing *firstly* that there has been a voluntary submission of the matter in dispute to an arbitration of one or more persons; *secondly* that it was agreed by the parties either expressly or by implication that the decision of the arbitration will be accepted as final and binding; *thirdly* that the said *arbitration was in accordance with the custom of the parties or their trade and business*; *fourthly* that the arbitrators reached a decision and published their award and *fifthly* that the decision or award was accepted at the time it was made (*Eke v Okwaranyia* (2001) 86 LRCN 1403 at 1429).

Now, in the case under study between *Ogwezzi-Amacha* and the *Basilica of Grace, Abbi* there is no doubt that there was a customary arbitration at the Palace of His Royal Highness *Uzu Nwachukwu* and the decision of the Palace was published in the judgment of the Palace of the *Ukor-Okpala-in-Council* endorsed by one of the most prominent Chiefs of *Abbi* in recent times

as the Secretary to the Palace, Chief *Ojo Enueweosu*. But can the judgment which awarded the land in dispute in the customary arbitration to the Church be regarded as estoppel in the light of the continued litigation of the parties and the fact that the matter and the award has not been pronounced upon by any court of law? The authorities of the Supreme Court cited in this study have not clearly shown that the arbitral award must be adopted before a court of law as the judgment of the court before it can be treated as estoppel. But it is extant on the authorities of the Supreme Court that *Ogwezzi-Amacha* family which lost at the customary arbitration has the freedom to disavow the award. And that the family had clearly done by conveying the land to third parties who are waging proxy litigation against the Church at *Abbi* and which proxies have successfully destroyed all the economic trees, Dispensary and Maternity on the land.

Theory of interlocutory injunction

A critical examination of what played out before the trial District Customary Court *Abbi*, the Delta State Customary Court of Appeal, Cable Point *Asaba*, High Court of Justice, *Kwale* and the Court of Appeal, *Asaba* with regards to the nature of the applications filed and argued before the Courts reveal that they were essentially interlocutory. The theory of interlocutory injunction is confined within the praxis of procedural law. The golden principles of interlocutory application are that it is brought before the court in order to preserve and maintain the *res in litigation* and to bring the subject matter in litigation within the control and domain of the court so that it is not destroyed or dissipated before the conclusion of the matter. It must also be demonstrated that there is a serious issue to be tried and a legal right exists with the Church (as the customary arbitral award showed in this case under study). It must also be shown that damages cannot be adequate compensation to the applicant and the balance of convenience is in the applicant’s favour. The applicant must be timely in bringing up the interlocutory application as delay defeats equity; undertake to pay damages if it is granted and it is later found to be frivolous; and most essentially, it must be

made clear that the acts sought to be restrained have not occurred as the court cannot restrain an act that has been done or carried out (Suit No B/346/2021 Ikpea & Anor. v. Isaac Ogbewe & 6Ors per Hon. Justice P. A. Akhiero citing: Kotoye v. CBN (1989) 1 NWLR (Pt.98) 419; Buhari v. Obasanjo (2003) 17 NWLT (Pt.850) 587 and Adeleke v. Lawal (2014) 3 NWLR (Pt.1393) 1 at 5).

There is no doubt that although accompanying the writ of summons in the case between the Basilica of Grace and Ogwezzi-Amacha family of Abbi caused a lot of disservice to the parties to the case, it was clear that an injunction was necessary because the acts of the Ogwezzi-Amacha family and its privies in plundering the land of the Church was continuing such that even at the Court of Appeal, Asaba in CA/B/85/2017 another application for interlocutory injunction was raised and filed and moved before their Lordships but again, it was refused 'with a wave of the hand by their Lordships' and that encouraged a lot of brigandage by the Ogwezzi-Amacha family and its privies. The intention of the Counsel to the Church (which was dictated by the representatives of the Church) was that having had an arbitral award in its kitty from the Traditional Council, the foreplay of an injunction would be a walkover but it eventually turned out to be an albatross for the Church and when the Church took out an appellate excursion to the Delta State Customary Court of Appeal believing that the trial court would be rein in, the outcome was the most disastrous. As a matter for the records, the Court vide the ruling of Honourable Justice V. I. Ofesi demonstrated that it was out of the tune of the times. His Lordship stated in outright scolding and teaching of the endeavour of the Counsel to the Church that, 'The modern trend is for appellant to appeal against an interlocutory decision of a lower court in an appeal against the final decision. See the case of Onwubuariri v. Igboasoyi (2011) All FWLR (Pt.569) 1059 at 1062. In fact, the Court of Appeal in the case of Obieuwenbi v. CBN (2011) All FWLR (Pt.575) 208 at 212 ratio 4 was emphatic and said: "Interlocutory appeals should be discouraged

...as it is unnecessary" ... While we will resist the temptation of going into the merit or otherwise of the main appeal, we can safely say that an appeal against an interlocutory ruling that questions the exercise of a Judge of his discretion to our mind is *a luxury that needs urgent review.*'

Furthermore, although the appeal which the Ogwezzi-Amacha family took out against the judgment of the High Court of Justice, Kwale was not an interlocutory appeal, it was also futile in the configuration of the ultimate desire of the civil justice system and the State that litigation should come to end timely. The appeal to the Court of Appeal in CA/B/85/2017 to restore the judgment of the trial District Customary Court, Abbi which dismissed the case of the Church without going to the merits on the grounds only that the High Court of Justice was not only a demonstration of an attitude actuated towards delay of the course of justice in that it was hitched on technicality, it was an exercise in futility as it could not have thrived at all because the said rulings of the trial District Customary Court, Abbi where within the well of the High Court of Justice, Kwale before the final submissions were made. Because of these multiple preliminary applications and those primed on technicalities, the case has remained un-determined before the Ndokwa West Area Customary Court, Kwale where the High Court, Kwale ordered it to start de novo and which order was affirmed by the Court of Appeal, Asaba on 5th June, 2023.

Literature review

Honourable Justice V. I. Ofesi while delivering an interlocutory judgment of the Customary Court of Appeal, Delta State of Nigeria holden at Asaba on 10th June, 2015 in Suit No. DCCA/5A/2015 The Registered Trustees of Diocese of Ndokwa Church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion) v. Femi Ojuyemi & 6ors reproduced the claim of the Church as filed before the trial District Customary Court Abbi in ADCC/22/2013 on 22nd August, 2013 as the substantial facts of the case before the Court. In the maiden edition of Delta State Customary Court of Appeal Law Reports wherein the ruling

of Hon. Justice V. I. Ofesi was reported at pages 49 to 61, the Editor of the Report (2020 1 D.C.C.A.L.R.) captured the claim of the Church as the facts in the report as follows:

The plaintiff is the owner of St. John's Anglican Church (Basilica of Grace) Abbi while the defendants are members of Umu-Onyugba Street Abbi. Many years ago, Abbi Community had granted the plaintiff a large parcel of land situated at Umu-Onyugba Street, Abbi where the plaintiff built and managed Umia Primary School (Location 2) and the Maternity as a Church Missionary Society (CMS). That sometime ago, the Government took over Schools from Missions and consequently fenced off the Umia Primary School (Location 2) compound and acquired same leaving the Maternity for the plaintiff to continue to run and manage. That while in occupation and management of the land, premises, maternity and its appurtenances, the defendants invaded the plaintiff and took over same *vi et armis* without the consent and permission of the plaintiff first had and obtained. The plaintiff swiftly summoned the defendants before the Traditional Council in a customary arbitration and obtained customary judgment against the defendants. Yet, the defendants went headlong on to the land and sealed off the Maternity and its Quarters and appurtenances and caused wanton damages to the plaintiff's economic crops and trees on the land and premises.' Consequently, the plaintiff claimed against the defendants as follows, 'a declaration that the plaintiff is entitled to the customary rights of occupancy over all that land situated at Umu-Onyugba Street, Abbi where it has a Maternity; an order of perpetual injunction restraining the defendants, their agents and privies from interfering with the plaintiff's occupation of the land. General and special damages in the sum of N100,000.00

On 2nd September, 2013 the defendants counter-claimed through their Solicitor, C. J. Enegide Esq. of 1, Law Office Close, Off Boundary Road, G. R. A. Benin City as follows, '...the defendants ...are members of Ogwezi-Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street, Umia Quarters, Abbi' which 'is the owner of the vast area of land

along Umu-Onyugba Street bounded by their adjoining lands on the left, right and at the rear by Umu-Okpala family of Inam Abbi. The land formed part of the vast land *the Traditional Council of Abbi forcibly took from the defendants' said family and permitted the plaintiff to use and run a Maternity ostensibly for the benefit of the entire Abbi community ab initio.*' The plaintiff denigrated, abused and illegally exceeded the restrictive right of use aforesaid and indeed subsequently abandoned the said premises prompting the defendants and their said family to repossess same, ownership haven reverted to them under Ukwuani customary land law applicable to Abbi.'

The defendants proceeded to claim as follows, 'a declaration that the said Ogwezi-Amacha family is the bonafide original owner of the land in dispute situate along Umu-Onyugba Street; a declaration that the forcible taking over of their land, the purported handing over of same to the plaintiff for use as Maternity without their consent and the denigration, abuse as well as despicable acts of abandonment of same by the plaintiff constitutes trespass *ab initio* and surrender of same under customary law; an order of perpetual injunction restraining the plaintiff or anyone acting on its behalf to desist forthwith from further harassment, intimidation, unauthorized entry, or disturbing the defendants or any member of Ogwezi-Amacha family from continuing to enjoy their ownership and possessory rights over their said land in any manner howsoever.

In addition to the facts already captured by their Lordships in the Law Report (2020 1 D.C.C.A.L.R) Rev. Stanley Adunkwu, the Synod Secretary of the Dioceses deposed to an affidavit in which he stated as follows, 'that the correspondences leading to the survey of the premises of the School and Maternity by the Church include a letter dated 2nd October, 1956 to the Ag. Synod Secretary, Mr. Hawkins, letter of Hon. Ejike Chidolue to the Secretary Niger Diocesan Synod of 30th October, 1956; letter of Ag. Secretary, C. M. S. Niger Mission to Hon. Ejike Chidolue (Licensed Surveyor and Architect) dated 31st October, 1956. A rough plan of C.M.S new site Abbi showing the original dimensions of the land and its boundary

neighbours as open grassland in the north, Okwelle village in the west, Umu-Onyugba Umia village in the south and Abraka-Obetim main road in the east was also exhibited. The written submissions of Rev. Cannon (now Bishop) Osaji-Nwafili dated 17/7/2011 to the Traditional Council during the customary arbitration and the judgment of the Council endorsed by the Council's Secretary, Chief J. A. Enuenwosu JP, dated 7/11/2011 and photographs of the destruction of economic crops on the land were also exhibited.

The Basilica of Grace claimed that Umu-Onyugba people had been attempting to convey the land to third parties and had in conjunction with such third parties started altering the structural nature, status and composition of the land. They had mounted a sign post on the Maternity calling it Umu-Onyugba Health Centre. They had started to use the premises for youth gathering and meetings and chased away the servants of the Church. They had let in tenants to the appurtenances of the building constituting the Maternity. They had attempted to sell and convey part of the land to Ike Nwose (son of one Maggi Akpola a well-known and rich business tycoon in Abbi). The Church averred further that she had not abandoned the land but had continued to use same for religious, missionary and philanthropic missions. She had also continued to use the facilities for commercial spirits attached to religious and educational missions like sale of Christian literatures, Holy Bibles and books, worship items and religious garbs and gears.

Ogwezzi-Amacha case

The arrow head of the 'war against the Church at Abbi is Chief Augustine Osagwu.' He is a Catholic parishioner and neck-deep in all the traditional and communal cases and contentions in Abbi and his office has been easily identified as that of the 'Secretary to the Okpala-Uku-in-Council'. Although 'controversial' could have been an appellation to the name, Chief Augustine Osagwu does not look to bear it. In an earliest affidavit he had deposed to for and on behalf of his Umu-Onyugba Street, he had stated as follows, 'I am the party sued as 4th

defendant/respondent (*though not properly described as a Chief*). I am the current Assistant Secretary of the Echala Traditional Council Abbi. I am also a member and *opinion leader* in Ogwezzi Amacha family of Abbi, the family in original ownership, subsisting possession, ancestral and current residence of the area of land known as Umu-Onyugba Street part of which is in dispute. In the customary arbitration judgment which was written by the Secretary to the Uko-Okpala-in-Council, his predecessor in office, he was identified and captured as the fifth defendant.

He claimed that the facts presented by the Basilica of Grace through Rev. Stanley Adunkwu was misleading and vehemently denied them. He averred that their ancestors founded and deforested large swathes of farmlands and passed the lands unto them as descendants by inheritance and that some of the lands became '*strategically located and indeed well sought after by the Missionaries and Native Authorities ostensibly for development, administration and welfare of Abbi people in general.*' The Traditional Administration of Abbi community at the time was 'no longer in the Amacha family and the fragile senile Okpala-Uku and the Okwas were *hoodwinked or intimidated by the said Missionaries and native Authorities (in connivance with the more vibrant young chiefs and politicians) into forcibly taking over vast areas of land from their original owners without their consent.*'

During the colonial era, vast area of land (including the area now in contest) was taken over forcibly by the Traditional administration despite the protest from Ogwezzi Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba and Umu-Okpala family of Inam Abbi (the original owners). The Traditional administration *blackmailed the various families with the fact that the land was to be used for development and for the general benefit of the entire people of Abbi.* The Traditional administration entered into a loose relationship with the Church's predecessors in respect of right of use of the land strictly for Missionary education and establishment of the Maternity in the belief that it was to be used strictly for the benefit of the people of Abbi. The entire Abbi community also contributed financially and solely provided labour towards the building of the Maternity until completion before same was handed over

to the Church (CMS Mission) to run as a nonprofit and quasi charitable institution for the benefit of the community.

However, the initial purpose was defeated as the Basilica of Grace started running the Maternity for profit while discriminating against the majority of the people of Abbi by refusing to be converted to the Anglican faith. The community also subsequently permitted the then Native Authority to site and construct a Dispensary on part of the land while the Basilica of Grace used the remainder to establish and run an educational institution until they were taken over by Bendel State Government, later Delta State Government, and renamed Umia Primary School. The Ogwezzi Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street and the Umu-Okpala family of Inam Abbi came up with the allegation that the Basilica of Grace had abandoned the property and claimed that in protection of their reversionary ownership interest, they took over the abandoned property and allotted it out in exercise in re-possession.

The arbitral award

The dispute firstly came before the Traditional Council of His Royal Highness Uzu Nwachukwu, the Ukor-Okpala of Abbi on 7th November, 2011 and it was held as follows, ‘The Palace will not dispossess the Anglican Church of the land given to it for a very long period. This will create a dangerous precedence which might lead other original owners to claim their land to other missions and bodies. In view of the above, the Anglican Church should continue to be in possession of the land in dispute and use it strictly for the purpose for which it was given by the Abbi community. That is for educational and health purposes that will be beneficial to the community and mankind in general.’

The arbitral award did not go down well with the Umu-Onyugba people and they decided to convey the land to Ike Nwose (son of one Maggi Akpola Ugbana a well-known rich business tycoon in Abbi) who further conveyed to Charity Nkemdawu another tycoon. These third parties invaded the premises at different times. Ike Nwose hewed down the economic crops of the Church while Charity Nkemdawu at a later date

upon acquiring from Ike Nwose pulled the Maternity building. An attempt made by the Church through an interlocutory injunction to restrain the third parties at the trial District Customary Court, Abbi failed. The trial court held on 25th April, 2014 that the acts of the defendants sought to be restrained have all be completed as such, injunction cannot possibly lie against them. The Basilica of Grace appealed the ruling to the Delta State Customary Court of Appeal, Asaba in DCCA/5A/2015 canvassing in the Notice of Appeal filed on 14th November, 2014 after leave to appeal was granted by the said Customary Court of Appeal in DCCA/M/7/2014 that the ruling was against the weight of evidence; the trial court misdirected itself and erred in law in dismissing the application when the applicant satisfied the legal requirements for the grant of same; the trial court misdirected itself in holding that the acts of the defendant on the land have been completed when in fact they were continuing. While the appeal was pending, the trial court dismissed the case. The appeal became beheaded. Justice V. I. Ofesi in the ruling of the Customary Court of Appeal delivered on 10th June, 2015 held as follows, ‘Finally, it is our view that the interlocutory appeal before us in Suit No. DCCA/5A/2015 emanating from Suit No ADCC/22/2013 suffered sudden death as soon as the trial court dismissed the applicant’s claim ... This appeal cannot be sustained... because an interlocutory appeal presupposes the existence of a substantive case or suit.’

The trial court dismissed the case before it when the witness in the box declined to continue his testimony before the trial court on the ground of an allegation that the trial court had been compromised. Rev. Cannon (now Bishop) Nwafili was later to depose to an affidavit that the trial court illicitly received the sum of N300,000.00 from the third party who bought the land from Ogwezzi Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street and used the money to buy Toyota Camry car registered as KWC 683 AA. The allegation was stubbornly held by the witness that when the trial court received the allegation and an accompanying application for adjournment to enable the Church field another

witness instead of the Bishop who propagated the allegation, the trial court angrily dismissed the entire case before it instead of granting an adjournment and or a transfer of the suit to the President of the Customary Court of Appeal for reassignment to another Area Customary Court.

The records of the trial District Court, Abbi reads, Counsel ‘informs the court that his witness is unwilling to go on with this case and there is no other witness available in court, and by the reason thereof the plaintiff cannot go on. Therefore, Counsel asks for an adjournment to enable him call another witness... Court...According to Counsel for the plaintiff, PW1 is unwilling to go on and no other witness available in court. The Court will not wait for anybody. Since somebody has testified, this is a proper case whereby the Court should invoke Order X1 Rule 1 ...and dismiss this matter...the claim of the plaintiff in this suit dated 22nd of August, 2013 is hereby dismissed accordingly. No order as to cost.’ It is also interesting to note that in Justice V. I. Ofesi’s ruling of 10th June, 2015 the noble justice in an obita dictum upheld the position of the trial court when his Lordship stated as follows, ‘In the present or instant case, the appellant as could be observed from the court’s record of the lower *deliberately refused to continue with his case after fielding some witnesses...In our mind, the trial court was right in dismissing the plaintiff’s claim (though this issue is not part of the appeal).*’ His Lordship, Justice V. I. Ofesi then went on to propound, ‘While we will resist the temptation of going into the merit or otherwise of the main appeal, we can safely say that an appeal against an interlocutory ruling that questions the exercise of a Judge of his discretion to my mind is a luxury that needs urgent review.’

Basilica of Grace Appeals

Again the Church appealed the dismissal of its claim before the trial District Court, Abbi to the High Court of Justice, Kwale through a certiorari in HCK/M/2/2015 The President and Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of the Federal Republic of Nigeria & G. C. Ojeh & 8Ors In Re: Registered Trustees of Diocese of Ndokwa Church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion) filed on 16th March, 2015. In a

Motion ex-parte for leave to apply for an order of certiorari to bring before the High Court of Justice for the purpose of their being quashed and transferred the proceedings of the District Customary Court, Abbi in Suit No ADCC/22/2013 The Registered Trustees of Diocese of Ndokwa Church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion) v Femi Ojuyenum & Ors filed on 15th March, 2015 a Litigation Secretary on behalf of Counsel to the appellant deposed as follows, ‘That during the pendency of the case at the trial court, the applicant/appellant *observed that the trial court presided by the 1st to the 3rd Respondents* (G. C. Ojeh Esq., C. E. Ilomechine and F. K. Ochonogor) has been compromised by the other respondents and their agents, privies and assigns. The representatives of the applicant, Rev. Cannon Phillip Osaji-Nwafili and Rev. Duru both of Anglican Church, Basilica of Grace Abbi and Rev. Stanley Chukwudi Adunkwu of Anglican Church, Obiarukwu informed me and I verily believed them as follows: that since the commencement of the suit through to the two rulings of 25th April, 2014 and 9th May, 2014 they have held the trial court in suspicion of partiality, bias, corrupt practices, victimization and insensitivity and have been pandering to the respondents because of ‘tycoon money’.

‘The trial court has not been impartial and it had been complained to applicant’s Counsel by the representatives of the applicant and the claim is rife that the 1st respondent got an illegal gift of a Toyota Camry car from the agents of the respondents who acquired the land in dispute and fenced in the buildings of the applicant/appellant. In fact, the Presiding Officer is on the pay roll of one businesswoman called Maggi Akpola Ugbanda who has financed the alleged purchase of the land in dispute and who had given the Presiding Officer the gift of a car and had given the respondents the money with which the land has been fenced and who has also placed tenants on the property of the applicant and which tenants are there on the Maternity and premises and who also ordered the cutting down of the economic crops of the applicants. That because of this observation the applicant’s representatives became no longer

sure of the evenhandedness of the court in the trial of the suit and instructed the applicant's Counsel to apply for the transfer of the case on several occasions but the trial court refused to accede to the prayers.

‘That the applicant appealed against the rulings of 25th April, 2014 and 9th May, 2014 to the Delta State Customary Court of Appeal and equally prayed for the transfer of the substantive suit to another District or Area Customary Court. That the ruling from the Delta State Customary Court of Appeal granted applicant leave to appeal and struck out the prayer for transfer. That on 13th March, 2015 when the case came up before the trial court, the applicant again resumed its application to transfer the case to another court because of the attitude of the court and the other respondents who constitute the whole Street and come to besiege the court on every date of hearing to heckle applicant's Counsel to the approval of the Presiding Officer. *Because of the attitude of the respondents and the trial court, applicant's Counsel has continued to face discomfiture in appearing in the hostile court.*

‘The hostility of the respondents has led to the transfer of the representatives of the applicant (Rev. Nwafili and Rev. Duru) out of the Abbi Parish and have refused to come back to court for fear to continue to testify in the trial. On 13th March, 2015 when applicant's Counsel informed court that the witness was no longer willing to testify because of the threat to his life and his lack of confidence in the court and requested that the matter be transferred hinting that this application for certiorari had been made to this High Court of Justice, Kwale the trial court overruled the Counsel and urged Counsel to proceed. Upon applying for another date to enable the applicant arrange for another witness the court dismissed the case. The conduct of the trial court is unfair, biased and compromised. The trial court is bent on stifling the case of the applicant and shutting it out of the temple of justice.’

Legal arguments in certiorari

The question that came up for determination before the High Court was whether the Basilica of Grace had made out a case to warrant the

exercise of the discretion of the High Court of Justice to grant an application for leave to issue certiorari or prohibition and therefore an order for the transfer of Suit No ADCC/22/2013 to another District or Area Customary Court. It was submitted that a decision of a trial court may be perverse where the trial judge takes into account matters which he ought not to have taken into account or where the judge shuts his eyes to the obvious (*Agina v. Agina* (1991) 4 NWLR (Pt. 185) 358 at 371). It was argued that the District Court shut its eyes to the complaint that the Presiding Officer was not qualified to hear the case because he has been compromised which has completely robbed the trial court of its jurisdiction to adjudicate and determine the matter. The indictment in vivid characterization was sufficient for the trial court to disqualify itself from the suit and transfer same to another court but it continued to play the ostrich even after several applications on the issue has been made to it (*Madukolu v. Nkemdilim* (1962) 1 All NLR 587). Nothing excites disenchantment from the rule of law, the judiciary etc more than the impression of a litigant that the Presiding Chairman has been compromised.

In this case, the applicant/appellant was not conjecturing or speculative but assertive. In *Orugbo v. Una* (2002) 103 LRCN 2391 at 2395 it was held that to establish bias, the judge must be shown to have pecuniary or proprietary interest in the subject matter of the dispute or it is the attitude displayed by the judge, if the attitude is apparent, that may be examined as to whether he was biased or the judge can be shown to have demonstrated favouritism to the respondents and hostility to the applicant. The applicant demonstrated the hostile environment of the court; how its witnesses have been transferred and refused to continue with the case; how its Counsel was being heckled; how all applications before the court had never seen the light of day except the one for accelerated hearing. In short, the trial court was accused of being hungry and thirsty for jurisdiction when in fact the applicant does not want the matter decided by the panel. Where a trial court goes on an unguarded journey in search for jurisdiction, appellate courts will call him to order (*Arjay Ltd*

v Airline Management Ltd. (2003) 108 LRCN 1173 at 1224).

In certiorari proceedings the court is mainly concerned with whether the record on the face of it showed errors or jurisdictional irregularities which must be corrected by quashing the record of the inferior tribunal (*Egware v. Governor, Bendel State* (1991) 3 NWLR (Pt. 178) 199 at 209. The order of the trial court dismissing the claim of the applicant when an application for adjournment is made to field another witness was wrong. It was even worse when the trial court was being asked to disqualify itself from adjudicating on the matter for being compromised. The trial court instead of absolving itself from the mud chose to imbibe in it and at the end of the day has descended into the arena of conflict. Bias is an inclination, bent, a preconceived opinion or disposition to decide a cause or an issue in a certain way which does not leave the mind perfectly open to conviction. Justice must be rooted in confidence and confidence is destroyed when right minded people like PW1 Rev. Osaji-Nwafili (now the Bishop) go away and refuse to resume their place in the witness box with the impression that ‘the Judge is biased.’

On the 17th March, 2015 leave was swiftly granted by His Lordship, Honourable Justice O. Jalogho-Williams (Mrs.) and the Presiding Chairman of the trial Court, G. C. Ojeh Esq. and all the other eight respondents were put on notice of the application which became fixed for 27th April, 2015 for hearing. However, the indictment and the allegation against the court changed the battle lines and the colour of the contentions. The Presiding Chairman took to the offensive and directed his arsenal and attack to the Counsel of the Basilica of Grace deposing that ‘the representatives of the applicant to wit: Rev. Cannon Philip Osaji-Nwafili and Rev. Stanley Chukwudi Adinkwu lied to the Litigation Secretary as to the facts of the case’ as the Court and its members had had ‘no iota of interest whatsoever and by reason thereof they had always been neutral, objective, impartial and unprejudiced in the course of hearing the case’. The Chairman deposed further that the facts were not only untrue and misleading they tended

to defame his character. They were facts ‘cooked up’ by Counsel to the applicants and the representatives and Reverend Gentlemen of the Church ‘in order to maliciously defame the character of the first respondent for no just cause.’

The Chairman of the District Court made frantic efforts at deposing that ‘the applicant lied when it stated ...that the first respondent got an illicit gift of a Toyota Camry from one businesswoman called Maggi Akpola Ugbana’. The purchase receipt, proof of ownership and other particulars of the car were exhibited and the Chairman deposed further ‘that at the moment, Suit No ADCC/22/2013 does not exist before the first to the third respondents or any other court or tribunal.’ Stating that the Court and its members were not served with the processes of the High Court and that the application was ‘misconceived, malicious, vexatious, frivolous, baseless and bereaved of legal principles’ and ‘basically ideated to defame the character of the first respondent and tarnish the image and integrity of the honourable court’ and that the representatives of the applicant should be ‘deterred’ by the High Court, the Church got further infuriated.

Venerable Abanum who took over from the transferred officers of the Church came forward with more complicating indictment against the Chairman of the trial court and got the Litigation Secretary to depose a reply to the counter affidavit of the Church to the following effect, ‘that I was informed by Venerable Abanum (*who happened to be of the same Emu village with the Chairman of the Court*) and Mr. D.O.N. Obolu of Umu-Onyugba Street Abbi and I verily believe them that the first respondent had another illegal and corrupt deal over the adjourning land to the applicant’s land owned by Mr. D.O.N. Obolu. Mr. D.O.N. Obolu’s land was forcefully taken by the 4th to the 9th respondents in addition to the applicant’s land and sold to Madam Maggi Akpola Ugbana. Mr. D.O.N. approached the first respondent for assistance as the Chairman of the Court. The first respondent asked Mr. D.O.N. Obolu for the sum of N100,000.00 which he gave to the first respondent. When the first respondent was not forthcoming with the

assistance he promised against the 4th to the 9th respondents, Mr. D.N.O. Obolu approached the first respondent who then told Mr. D.N.O. Obolu that he would recommend a Counsel to him. After receiving the sum of N100,000.00 from Mr. D.N.O. Obolu and recommending a Counsel to him, the first respondent went behind Mr. D.N.O. Obolu and the Counsel to also collect the sum of N300,000.00 from the 4th to the 9th respondent while still presiding over these cases. First respondent is not worthy of his station.’

With the foregoing facts, the trial court was nailed and subsequently went underground in the matter and declined from further participation in the arena of the conflict. The 4th to the 9th respondents (the Ogwezzi-Amacha family) continued to retain their original Counsel, C. J. Enegide Esq. who rather than filing a counter affidavit against the application for certiorari and prohibition took to the filing of a Notice of Preliminary Objection on 27th April, 2015 complaining that ‘ADCC/22/2013 ...has been dismissed and appeal envisaged; and that the applicant’s motion is an abuse of court’s process as the reliefs sought are merely aimed at academic exercise in futility. The procedure for initiating an action in certiorari and prohibition has not been followed.’

Although C.J. Enegide Esq. was unavailable to adopt his written argument in support of the preliminary objection, and same was subsequently struck out by Honourable Justice O. Jalogho-Williams on 3rd June, 2015, his main plank of argument in the objection was that the judgment and rulings of the trial court was not laid before His Lordship, Justice O. Jalogho-Williams before leave was granted to the applicants (ex-parte) to bring the application on notice. But during the main hearing, they were all exhibited, as such, the court proceeded to judgment in favour of the Basilica of Grace as follows: Firstly, the Judge ruled, ‘I must state that where Counsel or any Counsel at all observes a wrong done by a judicial officer, Counsel must speak out and it is not enough to say that the allegation was made to bring disrepute to the court...That would only arise if same is done in bad faith. *But the records of the court on its own has*

shown that 1st respondent and indeed 2nd and 3rd respondents have openly shown bias and reasonable suspicion of all the things mention by Counsel to the applicant. 1st respondent did not conceal or cache the bias or reasonable suspicion. 1st respondent indulging one side over and against the other threw caution to the winds and brought whatever disrepute to himself.’

‘I must state one fact here; this Court cannot hold in a forum as this that any judicial officer is corrupt. This is not the forum for such finding. An act of official corruption must be reported to the appropriate authority for a proper investigation to be carried out and a decision taken one way or the other. This court cannot carry out such an investigation therefore this court cannot rule one way or the other on whether or not 1st to 3rd respondents were corrupt. The allegation before me is one that is more than what mere evidential value can be placed upon at this level. It is affidavit evidence. It is oath against oath. It is believing, one party and placing value on the affidavit of one party over and above the other before me. It is placing a lot of weight on one and disbelieving the other. This cannot be applied to the issue of corruption as such an allegation is too weighty to be decided at this level. As this court cannot make any findings on the allegation of corruption and I so hold.’

Having found that G.C. Ojeh Esq. brought disrepute to himself but cannot be pronounced as a corrupt judicial officer given the nature of the forum, the forum not being the proper one, His Lordship Honourable Justice O. Jalogho-William tackled the issue of bias as follows, ‘bias has been defined as a state of mind, incapable of precise definition or proof, whatever impression it may convey but it may arise because of personal attitude and relationship such as personal hostility, personal friendship, family relationship and a whole range of circumstances from which the inference of a real likelihood of bias may be drawn (Dunge v. Ndakwoji (1992) 1 NWLR (Pt. 216) 221). Bias in relation to a court or tribunal is an indication or preparation or predisposition to decide a cause or matter in a certain prearranged way without regard to any law or rules. In a case where bias is being alleged against a court or judge, it is not the real

likelihood that the court or the judge could or did favour one side at the expense of the other that is important, *it is that any person looking at what the court or judge has done, will have the impression in the circumstances of the case that there is real likelihood of bias* (Azuokwu v. Nwokafor (2005) 22 NSCQR 355).’

‘In order to prove bias therefore, there must be actual evidence upon which it can be based. Applicant has averred it in its supporting affidavit in paragraphs 4 – 14. Going through the records thereof, particularly the record dated 13/3/2015 where Counsel to applicant had again applied for a transfer of the said Suit No ADCC/22/2013 and a ruling was delivered, in that ruling which is before the court, the application like others that had come before it was dismissed. Counsel was then compelled by the court to go on with his case. PW1 who had opened his case would not testify any further as he, according to the record, felt unsafe in the court. So Counsel applied for an adjournment to call his next witness which was again refused. Counsel to 4th – 9th respondents applied for the evidence of PW1 to be struck out. This is the ruling delivered: “According to Counsel for the plaintiffs, PW1 is unwilling to go on and no other witness available in court; the court will not wait for anybody. Since somebody has testify, this is a proper case whereby the court should invoke Order X1 Rule 1 of the rules of this honourable court and dismiss this matter...in view of the foregoing, the claim of the plaintiff in this suit dated 22nd day of August, 2013 is hereby dismissed accordingly”.

‘This is to say the least an outburst of bias considering the surrounding circumstances of this case. In the first place, Counsel to plaintiff in the case had requested for an adjournment to field in his next witness – when the witness in the box would not go on with the case due to the hostile environment. Counsel to defence applied for this evidence of the said PW1 to be struck out...The court refused. And when the defence Counsel applied for striking out of the evidence of PW1, the court being a Father Christmas went ahead to grant him much more than he had prayed for and dismissed the entire case. This in my mind is an obvious show of high handedness and bias on the part of the court which owes a

duty to both parties to do justice. Justice is not one sided and/or for the defendants alone in this case and that is what the lower court had exhibited here. *From the averment of the 1st respondent (G. C. Ojeb Esq.), it is obvious that he may not only have issues with applicant but he also had issues with Counsel to applicant which he exhibited in court and he caused same to becloud his sense of reasoning which is most unbecoming of a judge.*

‘I must state that the test of bias is an objective test and not subjective. It is what right-minded persons who are aware of the circumstances or facts of a case say (Akoh v. Abu (1998) 3 NWLR (Pt. 85) 696. *In the mind of a right-minded person, the activities of the court in the conduct of this case gives room not just for mere suspicion but reasonable suspicion of partiality, insensitivity and bias. It is no surprise therefore that applicant has added corrupt practices to the phrase.* Would an ordinary citizen sitting in the court room in the course of the proceedings of 13/3/2015 and indeed every other day and watching the proceeding leave the court with the impression that justice was done? In this case, I think not (Atobatele v. Faseru (2013) 1 NWLR (Pt. 349) 20). *Before I conclude this judgment, I must state that a person who has a judicial duty to perform is disqualified from performing it, if he has so conducted himself in relation to matters to be investigated as to lead a reasonable man to suspect that he may have a bias or that he may have been compromised.* For the superior court to then uphold the bias complained of, there must be circumstances from which a reasonable man would think it likely or probable that justice would or did not favour one side unfairly at the expense of the other. It is for the reason so far enunciated by this court that the applicant’s application hereby succeeds’.

Judgment

‘An order of certiorari is hereby issued for the purpose of being quashed the proceedings of the Abbi District Customary Court, Abbi in Suit No ADCC/22/2013 The Registered Trustee of Diocese of Ndokwa Church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion) v. Femi Ojuyenum & Ors. The proceedings of the Abbi District Customary Court Abbi in Suit No ADCC/22/2013 The Registered Trustee of Diocese of Ndokwa Church of Nigeria

(Anglican Communion) v. Femi Ojuyenum & Ors is hereby quashed in its entirety. The said Suit No ADCC/22/2013 the Registered Trustee of Diocese of Ndokwa Church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion) v. Femi Ojuyenum & Ors is to be removed from the well of the Abbi District Customary Court and by the order of this court transferred to the Ndokwa West Area Customary Court for retrial de novo.’

C. J. Enegide Appeals

The Counsel to Ogwezzi-Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street took out an appeal on 3rd December, 2015 to the Court of Appeal, Asaba compiling the records unilaterally without the input of the Registry of the High Court of Justice, Kwale and the Solicitor to the Basilica of Grace, Abbi in a process commonly referred to as settlement of records. In the Notice of Appeal, the 4th to the 9th defendants now appellants complained in their grounds of appeal that the Originating Motion before the High Court was void abinitio; that the proceedings before the lower court were a nullity as same were conducted in utter violation of the appellants’ right to fair hearing; that the lower court erred in law in quashing the judgment of the Abbi District Customary Court, Abbi; and lastly, that the lower court erred in law in holding that the appellants’ counter affidavit before the lower court in challenge to the Originating Motion for certiorari and prohibition was invalid having been filed out of time.

In Mr. C. J. Enegide’s Appellants’ Brief of Argument filed on 17th March, 2022 wherein two issues were formulated for determination, appellants’ Counsel submitted on issue one that ‘the Record of Appeal showed that Counsel raised and substantially argued the vexed issue of want of competence in respect of the Church’s Motion Ex-parte and the Motion on Notice by way of preliminary objection to the jurisdiction of the lower court to entertain them’ as they were ‘merely an academic exercise before the Court.’ Critically, Counsel’s view was that as the orders and rulings sought to be quashed were not lodged before the lower court before the commencement of the proceeding, the lower court was in grave error in setting aside and

nullifying the judgment of the trial court as doing so amounted to ‘nullifying proceeding or judgment on which it had not set its eyes’. Counsel further picked holes with the inclusion of ‘The President and Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of the Federal Republic of Nigeria’ as the nominal complainant. On the second issue Appellant Counsel argued that the striking out of the preliminary objection was ‘most misconceived with the greatest respect’. It was canvassed that the lower court ought to have elicited from the 4th to the 9th defendants ‘the reason for the absence of their Counsel but preferred to accede to the oral request of the Church’s Counsel to strike out the processes challenging the competence of his application and the jurisdiction of the lower court to entertain same’. Counsel finally urged the Court of Appeal to allow the appeal, set aside the judgment of the High Court and restore the judgment of the trial District Court Abbi dismissing the case of the Basilica of Grace. The appeal failed badly and woefully with a cost of N200,000.00 in favour of the Basilica of Grace against the Ogwezzi-Amacha family of Umu-Onyugba Street, Abbi on 5th June, 2023. The Ogwezzy-Amacha family has appealed to the final Court, the Supreme Court.

Conclusion

One of the notorious conclusions that can be drawn from this paper is that the subject matter in litigation is still under plunder. From one sale to another to the highest bidder while the Basilica of Grace remains tenacious to her claim which is acknowledged by all and sundry in Abbi community. It is well known that the Ogwezzi-Amacha family took on an institution which is very tenacious about matters concerning landed property. The Church all over the world does not joke with the land. Those who want to take back from the Church of God what their ancestors gave to the Church in antiquity anchoring the drive and disputation on revisionism and reversionary right are likelier to be fishing in troubled waters than being on a mission that is possible. So much negative campaign has been heaped on Chief Augustine

Osagwu of Ogwezzi-Amacha family who incidentally is a tenacious member of the ‘fellow Catholic Church of Abbi’ and whose land was also granted in similar circumstances.

The role of trial courts in the determination of sensitive cases touching on land and involving institutions should be guided. Courts should be able to understand that as they decide cases, they are exposed to scrutiny which may not be obvious in the beginning but may play out at the end of the day especially through the appellate system. The remarks made against the trial court in this study could have been avoided if the trial court had been more discerning and conscious of the fact of the customary arbitration judgment that was starring at it throughout the course of the proceedings before it. To have turn a blind eye to it gave the Ogwezzi-Amacha family so much gusto, verve and impunity that led to so much plundering of the facilities of the Church on the property. The court ought to have known that it was dealing with an invincible spiritual entity as the Church has come to be seen in this part of the world. The campaign of Ogwezzi-Amacha family did not seem to be beyond the desire to make financial gain from the land seeing that the Church has come under heavy weather and the vicissitudes of her times. It is still believed that at the end of the day, the Church may call for reconciliation during which it may have to re-negotiate her claim to the land with the family as is the case with so many of such litigations that are currently classified as gold-digging litigations.

The stiff opposition which the Basilica of Grace has shown so far against the plot of the Ogwezzi-Amacha family is recognizable and commendable looking at the actual conduct of the family in conveying the land in dispute to third parties whilst the litigation was pending. It sells out the family as a ‘bunch of cheap’ land speculators parading as revisionists calling to set aside what their ancestors had kept in place in antiquity. The fact that the family does not have any concrete evidence of how its ancestors granted the land to the Basilica of Grace underscores the deviousness and spuriousness of their claim. At the Court of Appeal when their Lordships decided not interface with a Motion

for interlocutory injunction against the Ogwezzi-Amacha family, the words that their Lordships used to qualify its representatives and their conduct on the land and the oral threats their Lordships issued them were so scathing and vituperative that they subsequently shunned appearing in the appeals and even their Counsel had to farm out the brief to another Counsel to take the watershed judgment with punitive cost of N200,000.00 on 5th June, 2023.

Recommendation

- Churches in Nigeria should go about complying with the law in their modes of acquiring properties; so much is put on trust that does not pan out well at the end of the day.
- Natives engaging the Churches of old in modern battles in revisionism should know that they were given births to by their mothers who accessed ancient drugs against childhood diseases in those medical facilities they are plundering today.
- Rather than go for revisionist attacks, natives should revive Church facilities through collaboration with the Church authorities.
- Trial courts should look out for the signals and impose injunctive remedies pending the final determination of trial in order to take out the wind from the sails of tribal families like Ogwezzi-Amacha family whose conduct is being replicated in many ancestral communities hankering to take back from the Church what the ancestors gave to the Church in the time they were in darkness and dire need.

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